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✓ **Bio-organic preparations complying to reduce the load
of insect-pests on horticultural crops without environmental risk:
Conceptual evaluation**

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A study was conducted in hot arid regions of western Rajasthan (Bikaner, Churu, Sikar, Nagaur and Jodhpur districts) during 2012-2014. A total of 150 respondents were selected from different category of the farmers/ locale people under different areas of the study. The respondents were personally contacted, interviewed and also had group discussion with them to collect the targeted information / data on semi-structured interview schedule. The supportive data/ information were also collected from secondary sources and field workers. The purpose of study was to identify, collect and document the bio-preparations formulated and complied by the farmers to reduce the load of insect-pests on their horticultural crops without environmental risk in hot arid regions of western Rajasthan. Such major bio-preparations as identified and collected during the study were: (a) Powder of tumba fruits, extract of tumba fruits, cake of tumba fruits, tumba+ aloe + neem extract, tumba+ common salt + chilli (b) powder & extract of aak leaves (c) extract of karanj, leaves, cake of karanj, seeds, oil of karanj, seeds (d) Powder of neem kernel, extract of neem kernel /leaves, cake of neem karnel, oil of neem kernel, Tumba+ aloe + neem extract, asafetida + neem + chilli extract (e) tea wastage/ garbage (f) application of extract of castor leaves and castor oil + tumba extract (g) extract of Pilu + ker (h) In-situ burning of crop residues and farm wastes (i) extract of moringa leaves and cake of moringa seeds (j) extract of bitter type aloe vera (k) others - spray of Garlic derivatives/extracts, tobacco water, kerosene oil and ash mixture, dusting of cow-dung ash and FYM mixture, burning of mustard/sesamum oil in crop fields, coddung+ goat/sheep excreta + kerosene oil, butter milk/ curd in pits of fruit plants, hing (asafetida) solution, oil cakes and wooden ash in the soil, spraying of urine, cow dung and excreta of goat/sheep, castor oil with cow urine, etc.